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**ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE, MOTIVATION AND JOB SATISFACTION:
PERCEPTIONS OF ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AMONG LAWYERS**

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ABSTRACT

Organizational justice, motivation, and job satisfaction are interrelated concepts. Numerous studies and theories explore these concepts, and this study provides explanations and analyzes the professional characteristics of lawyers. Organizational justice refers to employees' perceptions of the fairness of the balance between their efforts, qualities, and rewards within organizations. Many studies have shown that the perception of organizational justice is linked to motivation and job satisfaction. A sense of organizational justice helps employees enjoy their jobs and workplaces, work more efficiently, and attain job satisfaction.

This study aims to explain the effects of organizational justice, which is closely related to the concept of justice, on the motivation and job satisfaction of lawyers, a profession inherently associated with justice. Furthermore, it hypothesizes that perceptions of organizational justice have a more significant impact on motivation and job satisfaction for lawyers compared to other professions.

KEY WORDS: Justice, Organizational Justice, Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Law

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INTRODUCTION

Justice is a concept approached from various disciplinary perspectives and can be defined in numerous ways. As is commonly understood in academic circles, justice is not synonymous with equality; in fact, absolute equality can lead to absolute injustice. This study examines the concept of justice within the context of organizational behavior—specifically organizational justice—and explores its relationship with motivation and job satisfaction, with a particular focus on the legal profession. Within this framework, a hypothesis is presented that the perception of organizational justice has a greater impact on job satisfaction for lawyers compared to other professions. This effect may be either positive or negative. However, due to time constraints, no conclusion was reached regarding the hypothesis.

1. JUSTICE

The concept of justice forms the foundation of ideas such as State Theories and Doctrines, as well as Human Rights and Freedoms. Its relevance to these core principles is the reason justice has captivated philosophers and scholars throughout human history. Contrary to popular belief, justice is not an abstract, distant concept; rather, it is a tangible necessity in our lives, as essential as food and water. It serves as the cornerstone of state existence and the establishment of security.

According to Aristotle, justice is the foremost moral virtue. It encompasses both adherence to laws and an understanding of equality. These two principles come together to create two forms of justice: distributive and corrective. Distributive justice is based on equality in terms of ability, and it relies on both arithmetic and geometric proportions; it governs the distribution of honor, fame, and wealth. Corrective justice, on the other hand, is based on numerical equality and focuses on visible equality, relying on arithmetic proportion. This type of justice is more common in democratic societies.

For Machiavelli, justice has a regulatory, legal, and libertarian character. He argued that for laws to be beneficial, they must support social equity and balance social forces. Without social balance and equity, the state cannot sustain order or progress, and respect for justice is directly proportional to its presence

1.1.1 The Concept of Justice

The concept of justice forms the basis of various doctrines and theories related to the state, human rights, and individual freedoms. Its enduring significance is what has made justice a focal point for philosophers and scholars since the beginning of human history. Rather than being an abstract, distant concept, justice is in fact a fundamental need in our lives, as essential as eating and drinking. It serves as the foundation of state existence and the assurance of security.

According to Aristotle, justice ranks as the highest moral virtue. It involves adherence to the law and an understanding of equality. By combining these two principles on a social level, two forms of justice emerge: distributive and corrective. Distributive justice, which is grounded in equality of ability, is based on arithmetic and geometric proportions and is relevant in the

distribution of honors, fame, and wealth. Corrective justice, on the other hand, is based on numerical equality and visible fairness, typically seen in democratic societies.

Machiavelli's interpretation of justice emphasizes its legal, regulatory, and freedom-oriented aspects. In his view, the effectiveness of laws depends on their role in upholding social fairness and maintaining a balance among social forces. In the absence of social balance and fairness, a state cannot sustain its order, and respect for justice is proportional to its existence

1.1.2 Elements of the Concept of Justice

Equality

As is widely known in academic circles, justice does not equate to equality; in fact, absolute equality can lead to absolute injustice. The application of a relatively abstract concept like justice to concrete situations, while accounting for specific circumstances, leads to the notion of equity. In a business context, equality of opportunity should be provided to all employees. However, equal pay for all employees may contradict equity, as individuals have different qualities. Thus, compensation policies should align with the structure of the work itself, taking into account varying employee characteristics. Otherwise, employees' perception of organizational justice will negatively shift. For these reasons, equality in the workplace must be designed to uphold equity.

Reciprocity

The element of reciprocity reflects the balance between the values exchanged in social and individual relationships. The closer this balance is, the stronger the perception of justice in the relationship. When employees feel that they are fairly rewarded—through wages, promotions, or benefits—in exchange for their effort, importance, and contributions to the organization, their perception of justice increases.

Rationality

Rationality involves making decisions based on logical reasoning and tangible evidence. From a justice perspective, it is crucial that decisions are grounded in predetermined criteria, eliminating arbitrary practices.

2. ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE

2.1.1 The Concept of Organizational Justice

In organizations, which are essentially living entities formed by individuals working together to achieve common goals, the concept of organizational justice is one of the most critical behavioral and psychological principles (Eberlin & Tatum, 2008: 311).

Organizations aim to maximize profits by utilizing their resources efficiently in their respective fields. To make the most of one of their most valuable resources—human capital—employees need to have faith in the organization’s fairness. Organizational justice has been defined in various ways.

Moorman defines organizational justice as the attitudes and behaviors of employees regarding the fairness of practices within organizations (Moorman). However, in my view, it relates more closely to employees’ perceptions of fair treatment rather than actual fair treatment itself. Similarly, Beugre and Baron describe organizational justice as a social phenomenon reflecting how employees perceive their relationships with colleagues and supervisors.

Moreover, Cropanzano defines organizational justice as individual assessments of the ethical and moral aspects of administrative processes; İçerli, as the perceptions employees hold regarding the allocation of organizational resources; and Tetik, as employees’ perceptions of fairness in organizational practices. It can be concluded that organizational justice in the literature is generally agreed to be an individual perception.

Studies on organizational justice indicate that beyond perception, concepts such as equality, ethics, interpersonal justice, consistency, and representation serve as foundational principles.

To foster a desired perception of justice within organizations, the following points should be considered:

- **Neutral selection of managers,**
- **Objective and transparent criteria for determining employees’ material benefits,**
- **Establishing mechanisms for information sharing, communication, appeal, and evaluation control, as well as a corrective system for addressing identified issues** (Karaeminoğulları).

2.1.2 Theories of Organizational Justice

Numerous theories have been proposed to explain employees' perceptions of justice within organizations. These theories can be categorized into four main groups based on two dimensions: content vs. process and reactive vs. proactive (Greenberg, 1987: 9-10; Çakır, 2006: 45; İçerli, 2010: 70-71).

Dimension	Content	Process
Reactive	Equity Theory (Adams)	Procedural Justice Theory (Thibaut & Walker)
Proactive	Justice Judgment Theory (Leventhal)	Distribution Preference Theory (Leventhal, Karuza, & Fry)

(Greenberg, 1987: 10)

2.1.2.1 Reactive Content Theories

Reactive theories examine employees' responses to unfair practices within organizations, while content theories focus on the fair distribution of resources, as addressed in process theories.

Reactive content theories center on employees' responses to perceived injustices, including avoidance or escape. Examples of prominent reactive theories include Homans' (1965) Distribution Justice Theory, Adams' (1965) Equity Theory, Walster et al.'s (1973) Equity Theory, and Crosby's (1976) Relative Deprivation Theory. These theories emphasize employees' negative reactions when rewards and individual benefits are perceived as unfairly distributed. It can be said that the concept of reactive justice arises almost simultaneously with the experience of injustice.

Adams' Equity Theory laid the foundation for understanding organizational justice, based on four main assumptions:

- Employees will work harder as their individual rewards increase,
- Employees tend to develop a work system that ensures fair distribution of rewards and wages within their workgroups,
- When employees perceive a departure from equality in their work environment, it generates stress, so maintaining equitable organizational relationships is essential,

- When employees feel they are in unequal relationships, they will seek to restore equity and alleviate stress.

Homans (1961), however, argued that distributional justice does not create an environment of equality; rather, equal distribution creates unfairness. According to Homans, distributional justice should be based on equivalency rather than equality, with equality determined by factors such as gains, profits, and investments (Çakır, 2006: 35).

According to this theory, employees have a transactional relationship with the organization in which they invest and expect material returns such as rewards, wages, and bonuses. When these expectations are met by the organization, a perception of justice forms; however, when these expectations are unmet, employees experience an unjust organizational environment (Meydan, 2010: 69). Homans argued that the distribution of organizational resources must consider employees' contributions, as equal distribution without regard to individual investments will lead to an unjust organizational environment.

Crosby's (1976) Relative Deprivation Theory also explains distributive justice using Equity Theory and is considered a reactive content theory. This theory suggests that comparing material rewards among employees of varying seniority allows them to gauge fairness. Employees may experience feelings of deprivation, resentment, or even psychological responses such as depression or anger when they perceive inequities. Implementing fair standards for resource distribution based on employees' performance leads to positive outcomes.

2.1.2.2 Proactive Content Theories

While reactive content theories examine employees' responses to fair and unfair practices within organizations, proactive theories focus on efforts to create fair practices and behaviors. This approach originated with Leventhal's Justice Judgment Theory (Greenberg, 1987: 13).

Leventhal's (1976, 1980) Justice Judgment Theory focuses on distributive justice and suggests that six key principles—consistency, impartiality, accuracy, correctability, representativeness, and ethicality—directly impact perceptions of organizational justice (İyigün, 2012: 56). According to the theory, individuals may apply different distribution rules based on circumstances to make fair distribution decisions. For instance, when maintaining social

harmony among group members is important, rewards can be distributed equally, disregarding differences in individual contributions (Yürür, 2005: 118).

Another proactive content theory, Lerner's Justice Motive Theory, diverges from Leventhal's approach, which considers justice-seeking as a means to maximize profits.

According to Lerner, organizational distribution practices can be based on four different principles, which are relationally oriented according to Justice Motive Theory (Özen, 2002; in Greenberg, 1987: 13).

- **Principle of Competition:** Suggests that distribution should be based on individual performance.
- **Principle of Equality:** Proposes that distribution should be equal under all conditions.
- **Equity-Based Sharing Principle:** Argues that distribution should depend on individuals' varying efforts.
- **Marxist Principle of Justice:** Advocates that employees' needs should also be considered in distribution.

2.1.2.3 Reactive Process Theories

Process theories explore the practices related to determining employees' pay and advancement within organizations.

Unlike content theories, which focus on the fairness of distribution in decision-making processes, reactive process theories examine employees' responses to the procedures through which decisions are made.

One of the most prominent theories in this category is Thibaut and Walker's (1978) Procedural Justice Theory, which emerged from studies on courtroom disputes and resolution processes. It identifies three parties involved in a conflict: two disputing parties and a decision-maker. The conflict process consists of the evidence presentation phase and the decision-making phase, which attempts to uncover material facts based on evidence. The theory introduces two concepts:

- **Process Control:** Refers to the extent of control disputing parties have over the process.

- **Decision Control:** Refers to the degree of control over the decision-making process that ultimately resolves the conflict.

According to this theory, practices that allow employees process and decision control generate more satisfaction compared to those that do not, and decisions following processes with process control are perceived as more just (Greenberg, 1987: 13-14; Irak, 2004: 30; İçerli, 2010: 77; İyigün, 2012: 37).

2.1.2.4 Proactive Process Theories

Proactive process theories focus on examining and implementing processes that establish perceptions of organizational justice (Greenberg, 1987: 10).

Distribution Preference Theory, a proactive process theory, suggests that managers determine which distribution processes to implement to aid in ensuring fairness. The theory identifies eight characteristics that promote a sense of justice within organizations (Greenberg, 1987: 14-15; İçerli, 2010: 77):

- The right to select managers,
- Consistent rules,
- Accurate information,
- Structured decision-making authority,
- Impartiality,
- Consideration of appeals,
- Control over processes,
- Ethical standards.

2.1.3 Types of Organizational Justice

Organizational justice can also be classified into procedural justice, interactional justice, and distributive justice. These types are examined in detail below.

2.1.3.1 Procedural Justice

Procedural justice refers to the fair, equitable, and honest application of organizational processes, including information gathering, planning, decision-making, participation in decisions, informing employees of outcomes, avoiding over- or underpayments, employee promotions and rewards, career planning, and performance evaluation and management (Folger & Konovsky, 1989: 118).

The objectivity and transparency of principles and criteria used in determining material benefits for employees, and even in all decisions affecting them, fosters a sense of justice. In other words, the belief that the decision-making process is fair reinforces the perception that the resulting outcomes are also fair (Çakır, 2006: 47).

2.1.3.2 Interactional Justice

Interactional justice concerns fairness in social interactions, focusing on the fairness of investments made in these relationships and the resulting outcomes (Demirel & Seçkin, 2011: 103).

Interactional justice entails that individuals affected by decisions are informed and given explanations about those decisions, fostering a sense of respect. It is based on four fundamental principles (Morland et al., 2011: 148):

- **Respect:** Individuals should be treated with kindness and respect.
- **Honesty:** People should be treated honestly in decision-making processes.
- **Justification:** Reasonable explanations should be provided regarding decision-making processes and outcomes.
- **Appropriateness:** Prejudiced and inappropriate expressions or perceptions should be avoided in communication within social relationships.

2.1.3.3 Distributive Justice

Distributive justice, developed based on Adams' Equity Theory, is a concept that pertains to fair distribution of decisions and outcomes within organizations.

Distributive justice requires comparing the material benefits employees receive from their efforts within the organization (Karademir, 2010: 90). Employee efforts are also assessed by

considering responsibilities, seniority, and expertise within the organization (Moorman, 1991: 845). It highlights the importance of fair distribution of pay, bonuses, and other material rewards among employees (Özen Kutanis et al., 2010: 529).

Maintaining objectivity and transparency in distributive justice encourages employees to work harder and helps establish a sense of organizational justice. Studies by McFarlin and Sweeney indicate that perceptions of distributive justice generally impact personal outcomes like pay and job satisfaction.

3. MOTIVATION

3.1.1 The Concept of Motivation

Motivation can be defined as the entirety of internal or external drives that encourage individuals to act in a desired direction. It represents the initial source of behaviors aimed at achieving goals, providing both the desire to act and the resulting strength. Motivation is said to influence individuals' behaviors across all areas.

In a business and operational context, motivation is an essential outcome of organizational justice to ensure the effective and efficient use of human resources. The fundamental assumption is that as perceptions of organizational justice increase, so will motivation. This, in turn, leads to higher performance, happier and more productive employees, and ultimately, lower turnover rates.

3.1.2 Types of Motivation

3.1.2.1 Intrinsic Motivation

Kaplan describes intrinsic motivation as unconscious behaviors and drives arising from individuals' inherent needs.

3.1.2.2 Physiological Motivation

Physiological motivations are the semi-conscious and unconscious drives aimed at fulfilling individuals' basic needs required to sustain life (Aşıkoğlu, 1996: 41-42). It can be said to relate to the lowest level of Maslow's hierarchy of needs.

3.1.2.3 Social Motivation

Social motivations are external factors driven by the requirements of social life, such as education, career, and status, which also stimulate internal motivations.

3.1.2.4 Psychological Motivation

Psychological motivations are psychological factors and drives that move individuals to act, shaping their personality and behavioral patterns. Psychological motivations can be innate or acquired. In my opinion, the focus on the concept of courage within the discipline of psychology is an effort to foster psychological motivation.

3.1.3 Motivation Theories

Four major motivation theories have been proposed in this context: Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory, Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, McClelland and Alderfer's Motivation Theory, and Victor H. Vroom's Expectancy Theory.

3.1.3.1 Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory

Maslow examined human needs in a hierarchical order. This hierarchy forms a pyramid, moving from basic needs at the bottom to luxury needs at the top. Thus, an individual cannot sense the need for a higher level until the lower-level needs are satisfied.

3.1.3.2 Types of Needs

3.1.3.2.1 Physiological Needs

The most basic needs for survival, such as food and water.

3.1.3.2.2 Safety Needs

The need for self-protection and feeling secure. It is the primary need after physiological needs.

3.1.3.2.3 Social Needs

Every person has desires to love, be loved, and form relationships. As the needs lower in the pyramid are met, social needs, such as forming relationships and a sense of belonging, emerge.

3.1.3.2.4 Esteem Needs

In addition to love and affection, individuals also want to be respected. Once the previously mentioned needs are met, individuals feel the need for recognition, social position, status, achievement, and respect.

3.1.3.2.5 Self-Actualization Needs

The need for individuals to understand themselves, be aware of their characteristics, and pursue creativity. In the literature, this is referred to as the need for self-actualization (Bilgi, 2010: 14).

3.1.3.3 Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory is one of the most well-known need theories in the literature after Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory, and it is also one of the most important theories related to job satisfaction. Herzberg investigated factors that demotivate employees and those that encourage them to work harder. This theory differs from the hierarchy theory as it directly relates to organizational and work life.

The Two-Factor Theory aims to identify employees' expectations from working conditions, sources of motivation, and reasons for dissatisfaction with job conditions.

According to the Two-Factor Theory, the factors influencing job satisfaction and dissatisfaction are controlled by management. Herzberg categorized factors affecting motivation into hygiene (external) factors and motivators (internal) factors.

Hygiene factors include elements like pay, salary, and occupational health and safety. While these factors do not motivate employees, they are essential for maintaining motivation. Without these factors, individuals cannot be motivated (Bilgi, 2010).

Motivators (internal factors) are the primary drivers of behavior, providing motivation and satisfaction. The presence of these factors encourages employees, helps them embrace the organization, and provides a sense of personal accomplishment, thereby motivating them.

3.1.3.4 McClelland and Alderfer's Motivation Theory

Through his Need for Achievement Theory, McClelland argued that each individual has different needs, and fulfilling these needs contributes to job satisfaction and motivation. The theory focuses on three specific needs:

- **Need for Achievement:** The drive for growth, reaching standards, and a desire for achievement,
- **Need for Power:** The desire to influence others and steer them in a certain direction,
- **Need for Affiliation:** The drive to build close relationships with others (Stephen P. Robbins, Timothy A. Judge).

Research focusing on the need for achievement shows that achievement-oriented individuals reach the highest performance when they see a fifty-fifty chance of success, and the need for affiliation and power is closely related to management success. Successful managers tend to have a high need for power and a low need for affiliation (Stephen P. Robbins, Timothy A. Judge).

3.1.3.5 Victor H. Vroom's Expectancy Theory

According to Vroom's Expectancy Theory, job satisfaction and motivation occur only when employees' expectations for rewards are met. The more attractive the consequences of a behavior and the stronger the expectations about the outcomes, the higher the tendency to exhibit that behavior (Stephen P. Robbins, Timothy A. Judge).

In this theory, three relationships are discussed: Effort-Performance, Performance-Reward, and Reward-Goal (Robbins, Judge). Recognizing individual efforts, the fairness of rewards relative to performance, and their contribution to personal goals all influence motivation.

3.1.4 Practices and Job Design to Enhance Motivation

Over time, employees may lose motivation due to monotony or unmet expectations. To boost motivation, companies often implement practices such as job enrichment, job enlargement, changes in reward and compensation policies, and flexible benefits.

Job design refers to efforts to alter the content or structure of work to eliminate job dissatisfaction caused by simple, monotonous, routine, and repetitive tasks.

One job design technique is **job simplification**, which involves breaking down jobs into the simplest possible tasks to increase efficiency. This allows employees to quickly learn and perform these tasks accurately.

Job Rotation involves assigning employees to various activities and tasks related to their work to combat the monotony of routine tasks and boost motivation. The variation positively impacts employee motivation.

Job Enrichment aims to break routines by providing vertical job changes, such as combining tasks and creating work units. Vertical expansion means that the employee continues in the same job and position but takes on additional responsibilities, ultimately enhancing performance and satisfying the need for achievement.

Job Enlargement involves adding new tasks and responsibilities to the employee's current role horizontally. The employee's current job description remains the same. For example, if a social media admin's responsibility is to upload photos to Instagram, adding message management would be considered job enlargement, while adding the management of Facebook and Twitter accounts would be considered job enrichment.

Flexible working conditions are also a motivation-boosting practice. In such practices, employees can start and end work later on certain days or work from home on some days. This increases employees' sense of decision-making and belonging, alleviating the compulsion to physically be in the office. Flexible work is particularly effective and motivating for white-collar employees who don't necessarily need an office environment but rather a productive workspace and can work from anywhere with a computer.

4. JOB SATISFACTION

4.1 The Concept of Job Satisfaction

Today, perhaps as a result of certain political and economic regimes, there is a prevailing view that humans exist to work and produce. Generating value-added ideas, products, or services, setting goals, and experiencing the sense of achievement that comes with reaching these goals all contribute to the concept of job satisfaction in work life. Individuals' positive attitudes toward their expectations and needs in life generally lead to life satisfaction. Job satisfaction can be considered a component of life satisfaction.

There are many definitions of job satisfaction in the literature. According to İlhan Erdoğan, job satisfaction can be defined as the general attitude of employees toward their work; however, he notes that this attitude must be positive, as a negative attitude would indicate job dissatisfaction (İlhan Erdoğan). Thus, it is more accurate to define it as a positive attitude arising from individuals' work experiences.

As detailed in Maslow's hierarchy of needs, individuals have various needs within their professional lives as well. The extent to which these needs are met in the workplace is directly related to job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is the result of employees feeling that their expectations are met in the workplace.

In another definition, job satisfaction is described as the positive attitude employees display when evaluating their workplace and work, as well as the sense of pleasure and happiness they experience while performing their jobs.

While numerous definitions of job satisfaction exist, it can be said that there is a consensus on it being an emotional state. Moreover, theories such as Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs and Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, both of which were discussed in the motivation section, also encompass the concept of job satisfaction.

4.1.1 Vroom's Expectancy Theory

According to Vroom's Expectancy Theory, individuals will exert more effort if they have high expectations of the outcome. The more their expectations are met, the greater their satisfaction will be. This theory emphasizes three key concepts: valence, expectancy, and instrumentality.

Valence refers to the degree to which an individual desires a goal they will reach through effort; expectancy represents the perceived likelihood that a specific effort will lead to a specific outcome. Instrumentality is the belief that a certain effort is necessary to obtain a particular reward (Aksayan, 1990: 13; Yüksel, 2000: 142).

4.1.2 Porter-Lawler's Success (Satisfaction) Expectancy Theory

Porter-Lawler's Success Expectancy Theory is an expansion of Vroom's Expectancy Theory, proposing that for an individual to succeed, they must also possess sufficient knowledge and skills in addition to the concepts of valence, expectancy, and instrumentality found in Vroom's theory. The concept of "role" is emphasized, suggesting that the individual's role perception must align with the role defined by the organization; otherwise, role conflict is inevitable. Another concept is reward fairness, where employees compare the rewards they receive with others. If the perception of organizational justice is negative, job satisfaction will decrease (Baysal, 2004: 164).

4.1.3 Equity Theory

The Equity Theory examines how the principles of equality and fairness affect job satisfaction. According to this theory, job satisfaction will occur when employees with equal tenure and performance receive equal material benefits. Otherwise, perceptions of equality and justice will be negatively impacted, leading to job dissatisfaction.

4.2 Factors That Create Job Satisfaction

Various factors influence job satisfaction. Initially, research suggested that the nature of the job itself determined satisfaction or dissatisfaction; accordingly, it was assumed that job satisfaction would increase as an individual's position and responsibility in their job increased (Erdoğan). However, it has become clear over time that individual expectations, along with job and workplace variables, also impact job satisfaction.

4.2.1 Individual Factors

Positive attitudes resulting from the fulfillment of personal expectations in the workplace also contribute to job satisfaction. Since employees' personalities and expectations differ, the factors

influencing job satisfaction also vary from person to person. Some employees seek challenges and the sense of achievement, while others prefer a peaceful, relatively calm work life.

Experience is another factor to consider when determining job satisfaction. Individuals new to the workforce tend to have high expectations, but the likelihood of meeting these expectations is low, making job satisfaction more difficult to achieve. In this regard, age, education level, and intelligence also impact job satisfaction on an individual level. This topic will be revisited in the analysis of job dissatisfaction among new lawyers.

An additional individual factor influencing job satisfaction is the employee's social and family situation. Employees with weak social and family ties tend to have low expectations for life satisfaction, and therefore low expectations for job satisfaction as well.

4.2.1.1 Job- and Workplace-Related Factors

4.2.1.1.1 Job Difficulty

One workplace-related factor affecting job satisfaction is the difficulty level of the job. If the job captures the individual's interest, provides a sense of learning and achievement, and aligns with the individual's drive for success and appreciation, it will enhance job satisfaction. Job variety, creativity, and requirements for specific knowledge and skills also engage the employee.

4.2.1.1.2 Social Status

The way a job is perceived by society is also a factor affecting job satisfaction. While some jobs grant the desired social status, there are others that, for cultural reasons, individuals may avoid. Performing a job that people generally prefer not to do will reduce job satisfaction.

4.2.1.1.3 Job Characteristics

Intrinsic job characteristics create satisfaction to the extent that they align with the individual's abilities. For example, a job may involve frequent travel, which can positively impact some employees' motivation and job satisfaction.

4.2.1.1.4 Salary and Rewards

Research indicates that salary is one of the most important factors. For less experienced employees, a sufficient wage may be enough to satisfy their needs. As seniority and salary increase beyond basic needs, comparison with the wages of other employees becomes a source of satisfaction. Thus, an organization's compensation and promotion policies, as well as perceptions of organizational justice, are critical to job satisfaction. In some cases, even if compensation does not directly meet an employee's expectations, a perception of fairness can still foster job satisfaction.

The material benefits employees gain from their workplace are not limited to salary alone. Although high-performing employees are not primarily motivated by rewards, a fair reward system can increase motivation. Conversely, awarding non-performing employees can decrease job satisfaction.

4.2.1.1.5 Promotion Opportunities

Employees seek advancement and promotion in their jobs. Promotion leads to increased income, social status, and respect. Employees with a strong desire for promotion will find greater satisfaction in jobs that offer advancement opportunities.

4.2.1.1.6 Relationships Among Employees

There are numerous organic relationships among employees in most departments, with the exception of a few fields like Information Technology. Relationships between employees and managers tend to have a greater impact on the job satisfaction of less experienced employees (Erdoğan). When managers allow employees to make decisions, respect those decisions, and give them space within the organization, it fosters a sense of belonging. Employees constantly monitored in their work and decisions feel unable to express their ideas, which decreases job satisfaction. As employees gain seniority, the impact of their relationships with superiors on job satisfaction diminishes.

4.2.1.1.7 Communication

Communication within an organization includes the sharing, status updates, and reporting of tasks. Lack of communication tends to impact job satisfaction more than the presence of

communication. Studies have shown that high levels of communication and information-sharing in the workplace do not increase job satisfaction; however, the absence of communication leads to dissatisfaction. Moreover, as employees' educational levels increase, so does the importance they place on communication.

4.2.1.1.8 Social and Fringe Benefits

Social and fringe benefits provided by the organization are one of the factors affecting job satisfaction. For entry-level employees with low salaries, it is challenging to allocate time or budget to activities that contribute to life satisfaction, such as hobbies, courses, or private health insurance. However, when organizations provide such fringe benefits, they directly impact employee satisfaction and indirectly enhance their job satisfaction and loyalty due to the positive image of the organization in society.

4.2.1.1.9 Job Security and Workplace Conditions

Job security and health are especially important for blue-collar workers in the workplace. Employees with lower educational levels, who are less adaptable and less likely to follow rules, pose challenges for both themselves and the organization. Employers are responsible for providing the necessary training and ensuring compliance with rules.

For white-collar employees, while there are fewer workplace conditions that directly affect occupational health and safety, these factors emerge as workplace conditions that must be suitable in every respect. Working in a modern, clean, and well-equipped environment enhances job satisfaction, while a poorly ventilated, cramped, or dusty office has a negative impact.

4.2.2 Consequences of Job Satisfaction

When considering all the factors influencing job satisfaction, the resulting managerial implications have made job satisfaction one of the essential elements of modern management. An organization's success can be measured by many criteria, the most significant being a humane work environment. However, job satisfaction is more relevant to the individual than the organization itself (Erdoğan).

5. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AND MOTIVATION

While organizational culture helps employees adapt to an organization, each individual remains unique and distinct from others. Managers in organizations need to be aware of these differences, identify the needs of employees, and determine motivational resources to meet these needs. Research indicates that one of the most important factors in fostering motivation is, without a doubt, the perception of organizational justice. Some of these studies include:

In a 1999 study conducted by Pillai and colleagues, a positive relationship was found not only between leadership and organizational justice but also between organizational justice and motivation (Pillai et al., 1999).

Trust established within organizations contributes to organizational justice and, in turn, influences employee motivation (Aryee et al., 2002: 267-285).

In a study by Liao and Tai (2006: 545-556) investigating the relationship between employees' learning orientations and organizational justice, it was concluded that organizational justice perception is a motivating factor for employees.

The primary goal of motivation practices in organizations is to align employees' objectives with organizational objectives, ensuring that employees continue to work toward organizational goals. This alignment benefits both employees and the organization (Örücü and Kambur, 2008: 86).

Motivation can be considered a hygiene factor and an outcome of organizational justice. The perception that employees' efforts will be objectively assessed and that organizational resources will be distributed equitably is expected to enhance their motivation (Sökmen, Birsal, and Erbil, 2013: 5).

According to Martin and Bennett, employees should be rewarded in proportion to their contributions to organizational goals, and distributions should be transparent. Otherwise, if employees perceive a lack of organizational justice, their motivation will be negatively affected, leading to increased absenteeism and turnover (Martin and Bennett, 1996: 88; Örücü and Özafşarlıoğlu, 2013: 338).

To foster motivation through organizational justice, principles supporting a balanced relationship between employees and the organization must be implemented and maintained (Görgülüler, 2013: 10).

In a study conducted in the healthcare sector by Abbasoğlu, a positive relationship was found between all sub-dimensions of organizational justice and motivation levels (Abbasoğlu, 2015: 27).

In a 2017 study by Kökalan and Şişman, it was found that perceptions of organizational justice among university administrative staff positively affected their motivation levels (Kökalan and Şişman, 2017).

In a 2017 study by Tanrıverdi and colleagues, a significant and positive relationship was found between employees' general perceptions of organizational justice and their motivation levels (including intrinsic and extrinsic motivation) (Tanrıverdi et al., 2017).

In summary, when organizations establish practices following certain principles without discrimination among employees and based on effort and performance rather than external factors, a positive perception of justice among employees is created. This perception undoubtedly influences employee motivation (Sökmen, 2013: 45).

6. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AND JOB SATISFACTION

Numerous variables have been examined to study the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction. Research findings confirm a strong relationship between perceptions of organizational justice and job satisfaction.

Justice is essential for creating and maintaining a healthy work life for employees. The concepts of distributive and procedural justice, in particular, have been emphasized repeatedly. As a reflection of justice in organizations, organizational justice affects both job satisfaction and life satisfaction.

In professional life, employees' job satisfaction is influenced more by the organizational environment than by individual tasks. Within this environment, employees' perceptions of decisions, resource distribution, and rewards are closely related to motivation.

Various studies have examined the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction and have concluded that as perceptions of organizational justice increase, so does job satisfaction (Robinson, 2004: 13). Some of these studies include:

In a study by Folger and Konovsky (1989), similar to the findings of Tyler, Rasinski, and McGraw (1985), it was found that both distributive and procedural justice were related to job satisfaction, although the nature of the relationship with job satisfaction differs between the two types. Distributive justice has a stronger relationship with job satisfaction, while procedural justice is more related to organizational commitment (Folger and Konovsky, 1989). Subsequently, a study by Martin and Bennett found that both distributive and procedural justice significantly affect job satisfaction variables (Martin and Bennett, 1996).

In a study conducted by Robinson in 2004, organizational justice was found to have a significant impact on employees' job satisfaction (Robinson, 2004).

In various studies conducted by researchers like Cobb and Frey (1996), Fryxell and Gordon (1998), it was observed that in organizations where perceptions of organizational justice are low, employees' job satisfaction is also low (Wasti, 2001: 36).

7. ANALYSIS OF THE PROFESSIONAL LIFE OF LAWYERS

The journey of a lawyer, which begins in law school, eventually takes form in the roles of attorney, judge, prosecutor, or academician. Apart from learning concrete and current norms, law schools also have the mission of instilling a general and universal perspective, including subjects like Legal Philosophy and Sociology, Legal History, and Human Rights. This may even be the most important mission, as concrete norms can change. Contrary to common belief, laws are not memorized article by article by lawyers; instead, the protected legal value is internalized. Each concrete case embodies and is assessed based on this legal value.

Questions such as, "What legal value is protected by this norm? Why is it protected? What factors did the legislator consider when creating this norm, and why was this regulation needed in society?" are often discussed, ultimately leading to an understanding of the significance of the protected legal value. This understanding guides lawyers toward the essence of justice.

Justice, fairness, and equity are vital for safeguarding universal legal values. For example, the importance of property stems from the inviolability of the home, and theft committed in a residence or at night is considered an aggravated offense because the crime violates the individual's sense of security within their own property. Ensuring security is one of the fundamental duties of states.

7.1.1 Legal Internship

The concept of justice is significant for young lawyers who graduate with these perspectives. Regardless of the path they choose—attorney, judge, or prosecutor—they must complete a legal internship of one or two years.

In professions where experience is valued, seniority and hierarchy are more prominent. As individuals gain experience, they benefit more from the positive aspects of the profession. However, young lawyers often face long hours, frequently being assigned tasks that others avoid, and are often expected to work overtime as a norm. For instance, it may be considered disrespectful for a junior lawyer to leave the office before a supervisor has finished working.

During this process, lawyers may also face the reality that cases do not always proceed fairly in courthouses, which can affect their job satisfaction.

Furthermore, the Attorneyship Law mandates that legal internships be unpaid, which may contribute to a negative perception of organizational justice among novice trainee lawyers.

7.1.2 Attorneyship

Once lawyers complete their internship, the increased material benefits they gain from their workplace enhance their perception of organizational justice and motivation. Increased

seniority brings financial rewards, promotions, and fringe benefits, which contribute to job satisfaction. Lawyers gain various authorities along with their position, while also earning social status and respect.

However, with authority comes responsibility. Unlike trainee lawyers who hold no responsibility, practicing attorneys must face a high degree of accountability. Professional responsibility requires caution, as even a minor mistake can delay or result in the loss of a case. This cautious approach extends to all stages of the work process.

Lawyers' work must be entirely accurate, complete, and comprehensive. In addition to their duty to the client, lawyers are also accountable to the Bar Association, which monitors whether they fulfill their professional obligations. Therefore, even the most experienced lawyers conduct detailed research to ensure that there have been no recent changes in relevant legislation or case law.

7.1.3 Judges and Prosecutors

Lawyers preparing for the judicial or administrative judiciary exams must pass a written exam before taking an oral interview. While passing the written exam requires disciplined study, the criteria and outcomes of the oral interview can be somewhat subjective and uncertain.

Upon passing the exams, candidates undergo a two-year internship, during which they spend most of their time at courthouses with judges and reviewing decisions. They also receive six months of training at the Justice Academy in Ankara before being assigned via an electronic lottery system. According to experienced judges, it is quite challenging for young judges who are newly trained and appointed to single-judge courts in rural areas to make distinctions and judgments in cases involving complex legal issues.

Like lawyers, judges must work with a high degree of caution. Lawyers who do not make reading a part of their life will find their knowledge outdated. Judges also have to deal with concerns about changes in assignment locations or even dismissal.

However, it is evident that the professions of judge and prosecutor confer social status. Especially in today's context, being a judge or prosecutor brings many rights and authorities, as

well as high respect. It may be said that this respect is even greater than that afforded to lawyers or academicians.

8. HYPOTHESIS

It can be stated that the perception of justice and its impact on life for lawyers is different from that of other professions. This difference is also reflected in their perception of organizational justice. Lawyers' perceptions of justice affect their attitudes toward decisions, practices, and material gains within organizations in a unique way.

For most people, the concept and perception of justice is abstract and possibly distant. It is not a concept they think about or devote time to in their daily lives. Although many people are aware that crimes and injustices occur, they generally believe these matters are being addressed and that justice is being served. However, in their professional lives, lawyers see that what is written in the law may not always be applied and that each case needs to be assessed according to its specific facts and circumstances. Just as in other social sciences that deal with human matters, "two plus two does not always equal four" in law. Furthermore, the authority making decisions is human, and subjective errors such as attribution error, contrast effect, and halo effect can sometimes lead to unfair and unjust outcomes.

Additionally, as described in detail above, unfair practices within organizations are also common due to the demands of the profession. The practice of working overtime without compensation, driven by workload and urgent situations, is present in many organizations. Seniority discrimination is sharply pronounced.

Given these circumstances, the hypothesis of this study is as follows: The relationship between lawyers' perceptions of organizational justice and their motivation and job satisfaction differs from that of other professions.

For some lawyers, this relationship may have a positive effect, while for others, it may have a negative effect. Some lawyers may react more strongly when faced with organizational injustice, while others may react less, having become accustomed to existing unjust practices.

Thus, this relationship may manifest in such a way that lawyers' motivation and job satisfaction are less affected when confronted with organizational injustice, or, at the very least, the belief that there should be no injustice in legal organizations may negatively impact their motivation and job satisfaction.

9. CONCLUSION

The concept of justice has intrigued and been studied by many thinkers for centuries due to its impact on human life. Its place in organizational behavior literature lies in the idea of organizational justice, which addresses fair treatment in decision-making and resource allocation processes within organizations.

Motivation is the initial drive behind individuals' behaviors aimed at achieving their goals, providing the desire to act and the strength to pursue those goals. Job satisfaction, on the other hand, can be defined as the positive attitude individuals display when evaluating their workplace and work, as well as the sense of pleasure and happiness they experience while performing their jobs.

Numerous studies have demonstrated the relationship between employees' perceptions of organizational justice and their motivation and job satisfaction. As perceptions of organizational justice increase, so too will motivation and job satisfaction.

However, due to lawyers' unique perception of justice, it is believed that organizational justice affects their motivation and job satisfaction differently. Further research could be conducted to test this hypothesis.

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